

Synthesis, structure, electrochemistry, fluorescent and DFT study of Ru^{II} complexes with pincer-type 2,6-bis-(*N*-methylimidazolylidene/benzimidazolylidene)pyrazine ligands

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Abstract : Pyrazine based CNC-pincer proligands 2,6-di-(*N*-methylimidazolium)pyrazine dichloride, 1; 2,6-di-(*N*-methylbenzimidazolium)pyrazine dichloride, 2 and their Ru^{II}-*N*-heterocyclic carbene (NHC) complexes bis-[2,6-di-(*N*-methylimidazo-2-ylidene)pyrazine]ruthenium(II) hexafluorophosphate, 3 and bis-[2,6-di-(*N*-methylbenzimidazo-2-ylidene)pyrazine]ruthenium(II) hexafluorophosphate, 4 have been synthesized and characterized by different spectroscopic techniques. Electrochemistry and emission spectra of the compounds have been studied. The voltammetric feature of complexes 3 and 4 are quasireversible to irreversible as it is evident from large ΔE_p data (>250 mV). Both complexes are fluorescence active in nature.

Keywords : *N*-Heterocyclic carbene, ruthenium(II), CNC-pincer, electrochemistry, spectra, DFT.

Introduction

Imidazol-2-ylidene has been of attraction in recent past¹ due to synthesis of *N*-heterocyclic carbenes (NHCs) who are potential catalysts²⁻⁶. *N*-Heterocyclic carbenes¹⁻⁹, derived from the deprotonation of 1,3-disubstituted imidazolium or benzimidazolium salts by appropriate external base or proper choice of metal salt gives the Metal-NHC (M-NHCs) which are used in metal-mediated catalytic reactions and exhibit interesting photo-physical properties²⁻¹³. Beyond catalysis, recently M-NHCs contributed interesting results as anticancer, antimicrobial and

antifungal drugs¹¹⁻¹⁶. Though initially the imidazoline NHC ligands were comprised of *N*-alkylated derivatives, but with the progress, the file enriched more by *N*-functionalized NHC by xylene, pyridine, pyrimidine, pyrazole, oxazole, thiazole, carbazole etc.^{2-10,15-24}.

The *N*-alkylated NHCs mainly act as monodentate ligands, where as incorporation of wingtip like xylene/pyridine/pyrimidine/oxazole/thiazole in the backbone offer either mono, bi or tridentate NHC depending upon the designing of the ligand and choice of metal. Recently, tridentate organometallic pincer complexes¹⁸⁻²⁴ attracted

much more attention because of their widespread application in catalysis, biological applications and photophysical properties. In this regards, especially, pincer NHC complexes are very useful²⁰⁻²⁹. As they are strong σ -donor and weak π -acceptor than phosphine which enhance the electron density on metal and improves the catalytic activities. It is needless to mention, pincer carbene complexes should be much more stable than the other similar types of complexes because of the chelate effect (strong metal-carbon bond), which resist the complex from oxygen, moisture and heat³⁰⁻³⁴. In the literature there are huge examples of organometallic pincer ligand where donor centers are COS, OCS, CNS, CCN, NNC, CNC etc., where pyrazole, thiazole, pyrimidine and mostly pyridine are used^{2-10,15-24} as heterocyclic backbone with other C-donor center like benzene or substituted benzene. In the CNC pincer metal-N heterocyclic carbene com-

plexes mostly pyridine used as wingtip³⁵, but there are limited reports of pyrazine^{6,36,37} bridged imidazole or benzimidazole ligands which inspires us to design the ligand.

Recently Ru^{II}-NHC complexes^{21,22,38-40} bearing various *N*-heterocyclic carbene (NHC) ligands were synthesized, and their photophysical, electrochemical, and electrogenerated chemiluminescence (ECL) properties were discussed to evaluate a potential of their use as multicolor ECL labels. Interestingly, they exhibited multicolor ECL labels, which make us interested to study the spectra of our synthesized complexes.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization of the complexes :

The ligands **1** and **2** have been synthesized in 80–86% yield by reported procedure from the respective precursors^{6,36}. The presence of *NCHN* proton in ¹H NMR spectrum (in CD₃CN) confirmed their formation. The *NCHN* proton in ¹H NMR spectrum appeared at 9.47 ppm for ligand **1** and at 9.97 ppm for ligand **2**. The 0.50 ppm downfield shift for ligand **2** than ligand **1** is observed in case of ¹H NMR spectrum and 4.5 ppm downfield shift in ¹³C NMR spectrum. Complex **3** was prepared in 58% yield by the complexation of ligand **1** with RuCl₃·3H₂O in refluxing ethylene glycol solution at 180 °C (Scheme 1). Complex **4** was prepared (in 51% yield) by the

Scheme 1. When 2,6 position of pyrazine is 1-methylimidazole, the ligand is **1** and Ru complex is **3**; when 2,6 position of pyrazine is 1-methylbenzimidazole, the ligand is **2** and Ru-complex is **4**.

complexation of ligand **2** and RuCl₃·3H₂O with refluxing in ethylene glycol solution at 180 °C (Scheme 1). Absence of imidazolium C2 proton, down field shifting of pyrazine and other aromatic protons of complex **3** and **4** in the ¹H NMR spectrum confirm the formation of complexes. The crystals of **3** suitable for X-ray data collection were grown by diffusion of diethylether into acetonitrile solution. Crystallographic data for complex **3** are summarized on Table 1, and can be obtained free of charge from The Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif [CCDC-772881 (for complex **3**)]. Recently, crystallographic data of com-

plex **3** has been published by Lee *et al.*³⁷. To understand the electronic structure of the complexes **3** and **4** geometry optimizations have been carried out in DFT/B3LYP method. Structure of optimized geometry of complex **3** was drawn according to crystal structure and that geometry of **4** was optimized correlating with the structure of complex **3**. In optimized geometry, the Ru-C_{carbene} (M-C_{NHC}) bonds are found 2.098 Å for complex **3**, 2.099 Å for complex **4**, Ru-N_{pyrazine} (M-N_{NHC}) bonds are found to be 2.035 Å for complex **3**, 2.042 Å for complex **4** and bond distances varies 0.02 ~ 0.04 Å from crystallographic data. For complex **3**, N_{pyrazine}-Ru-N_{pyrazine} angle in optimized geometry is 179.9° [crystallographic data is 177.31(14)°], and that of complex **4** is 179.8°. In both complexes ligands are nearly perpendiculars to each other (88.77°) showing octahedral geometry. Bond parameters are listed in Table 2 and are found consistence with the previously reported (Table 3) data⁴¹⁻⁴³. The optimized structures of both the complexes **3** and **4** are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 respectively.

Table 1. Crystallographic data of complex **3**

	Complex 3
Empirical formula	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₁₂ RuP ₂ F ₁₂
Formula weight	871.56
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	<i>P</i> 2 1/ <i>n</i>
Temperature (K)	273(2)
Cell dimensions :	
<i>a</i> (Å)	20.3125(10)
<i>b</i> (Å)	11.0852(5)
<i>c</i> (Å)	28.8909(14)
α (°)	90.00
β (°)	99.5460
γ (°)	90.00
Volume (Å ³)	6415.2(5)
<i>Z</i>	8
Density (mg m ⁻³)	1.805
Absorption coefficient	0.699
<i>F</i> (000)	3472
Crystal size :	
Theta range for data collection	1.14–25.05
Index ranges	-24 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 24; -13 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 13; -34 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 34
Reflections collected	67145
Independent reflections	11340
Completeness to theta = 25.11°	0.998
Max. and min. transmission	23.24, 2.33
Refinement method	phi and omega scans
Data/restraints/parameters	67145/11340/928
GOF	0.940
Final <i>R</i> indices [<i>I</i> > 2σ(<i>I</i>)]	0.0477 > 0.1125
<i>R</i> indices (all data)	0.0650

Electrochemistry :

The cyclic voltammograms (Fig. 5) of the complexes display an oxidative response at high potential such as 1.39 V (270 mV) for **3** and 1.43 V (250 mV) for **4** respectively. The voltammetric feature is quasireversible to irreversible as it is evident from large Δ*E*_p data (>250 mV). The oxidations may be considered as metal-centered electron extraction. Upon scanning cathodically, a quasireversible reduction wave is observed in the potential range -1.30 V (Δ*E*_p, 90 mV) and -1.33 V (Δ*E*_p, 70 mV) along with an irreversible cathodic peak at <-1.75 V. The DFT computation of the optimized geometries of **3** and **4** can support the reduction at ligand dominated level; the HOMO, HOMO-1 etc. of both these complexes have >35% Ru character while LUMO, LUMO+1 carry >85% ligand character (Table 4). Thus redox response at anode may imply oxidation of Ru^{II} and cathodic couples are due to accommodation of electron at ligand orbitals.

DFT analysis :

To understand the electronic structure of the complexes geometry optimizations of **3** and **4** have been carried out in DFT/B3LYP method. Some selected optimized

Table 2. Selected bond parameters of **3** and **4** (theoretical and experimental)

Bonds (Å)	Complex 3		Complex 4	
	Theoretical	Experimental (CCDC772881)		Theoretical
Ru1-N3	2.035	2.010(3)	Ru1-N3	2.042
Ru1-N9	2.035	2.005(4)	Ru1-N9	2.042
Ru1-C1	2.098	2.052(4)	Ru1-C1	2.099
Ru1-C12	2.098	2.061(5)	Ru1-C20	2.099
Ru1-C13	2.098	2.047(4)	Ru1-C21	2.099
Ru1-C24	2.098	2.054(4)	Ru1-C40	2.099
Angles (°)				
C1-Ru1-N3	76.53	76.73(15)	C1-Ru1-N3	76.73
C1-Ru1-N9	103.5	103.71(1)	C1-Ru1-N9	103.3
C1-Ru1-C12	153.1	153.29(18)	C1-Ru1-C20	153.4
C1-Ru1-C13	93.12	90.46(17)	C1-Ru1-C21	93.04
C1-Ru1-C24	93.10	92.60(16)	C1-Ru1-C40	93.01
C12-Ru1-N3	76.53	76.62(17)	C20-Ru1-N3	76.72
C12-Ru1-N9	103.5	102.92(16)	C20-Ru1-N9	103.3
C12-Ru1-C13	93.11	95.00(16)	C20-Ru1-C21	93.01
C12-Ru1-C24	93.11	91.13(16)	C20-Ru1-C40	93.04
C13-Ru1-N3	103.5	100.67(15)	C21-Ru1-N3	103.3
C13-Ru1-N9	76.53	76.37(16)	C21-Ru1-N9	76.72
C13-Ru1-C24	153.1	153.36(18)	C21-Ru1-C40	153.4
C24-Ru1-N3	103.5	106.00(17)	C40-Ru1-N3	103.3
C24-Ru1-N9	76.53	77.06(17)	C40-Ru1-N9	76.72
N3-Ru1-N9	179.9	177.31(14)	N3-Ru1-N9	179.8

Table 3. List of bond parameters of CNC pincer Ru-NHC (*theoretical* data are written in *italics* font)

Sr. No.	Ru-C _{carb} (Å)	Ru-N (Å)	N-Ru-N	C _{carb} -Ru-C _{carb} (°)	Ref.
1.	2.062(5), 2.056(5)	2.061(4)	–	153.30(19)	41
2.	2.0551(19), 2.053(2), 2.0486(19), 2.048(2)	2.0177(17), 2.0198(16)	175.78(6)	153.81(8)/153.56(8)	42
3.	2.059(4), 2.073(4)	2.120(3)	177.8(2)	172.3(1)	43
4a.	2.052(4), 2.061(5)	2.005(4)	177.31(1)	153.29(18)/153.36(18)	Crystallographic data of complex 3 [CCDC772881]
4b.	2.098	2.035	179.9	153.1	Theoretical data of complex 3
5.	2.099	2.042	179.8	153.4	Theoretical data of complex 4

bond parameters are given in Table 2. The optimized geometries of **3** and **4** are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 respectively. The absorption and emission spectra of **3** and **4** is shown in Fig. 6 and corresponding λ_{max} values are given in Table 6. As expected for Ru^{II} complexes with d^6 electronic configuration, the first three high en-

ergy occupied molecular orbitals (HOMO to HOMO-2) have $d\pi(\text{Ru})$ and $\pi(\text{L})$ contribution (Fig. 3 and Fig. 4). But the contribution of $d\pi(\text{Ru})$ orbitals in complex **4** (38–50%) is significantly reduced compare to **3** (50–61%) (Table 4). Other high energy occupied orbitals (HOMO-3 to HOMO-10) have $\pi(\text{L})$ character with very reduced

Fig. 1. Optimized structure of **3** by DFT/B3LYP method.

Fig. 2. Optimized structure of **4** by DFT/B3LYP method.

contribution from $d\pi(\text{Ru})$ orbitals. The low energy unoccupied orbitals (LUMO to LUMO+5) have $\pi^*(\text{L})$ character with a HOMO-LUMO energy gap 3.60 eV and 3.63 eV in **3** and **4** respectively. For better understanding of electronic transitions in the complexes TDDFT calculations have been carried out on the optimized geometries of **3** and **4**. Some selected calculated electronic transitions for complexes **3** and **4** are summarized in Table 5. The calculated very weak HOMO \rightarrow LUMO transitions in the complexes are found at 465 nm and 429 nm in **3** and **4** respectively. The experimentally observed sharp peak at 400 ~ 410 nm in the complexes is an admixture of

Fig. 3. Contour plots of some selected MOs of **3**.

Fig. 4. Contour plots of some selected MOs of **4**.

Table 4. Energy and composition of some selected MOs of complexes **3** and **4**

MOs	Complex 3			Complex 4		
	Energy (eV)	% of composition		Energy (eV)	% of composition	
		Ru	L ¹		Ru	L ²
LUMO+5	-5.79	06	94	-6.04	02	98
LUMO+4	-5.80	06	94	-6.04	02	98
LUMO+3	-7.13	04	96	-6.62	05	95
LUMO+2	-7.18	0	100	-6.67	0	100
LUMO+1	-7.73	09	91	-7.32	08	92
LUMO	-7.74	09	91	-7.32	08	92
HOMO	-11.34	50	50	-10.95	38	62
HOMO-1	-11.67	61	39	-11.22	50	50
HOMO-2	-11.67	61	39	-11.22	50	50
HOMO-3	-12.49	0	100	-11.63	0	100
HOMO-4	-12.78	06	94	-11.64	0	100
HOMO-5	-12.78	06	94	-11.72	0	100
HOMO-6	-12.83	0	100	-11.79	0	100
HOMO-7	-12.87	0	100	-11.79	0	100
HOMO-8	-12.99	03	97	-11.96	16	84
HOMO-9	-13.12	0	100	-11.96	16	84
HOMO-10	-13.85	31	69	-12.46	0	100

Table 5. Some selected vertical electronic excitations of complexes **3** and **4** calculated by TDDFT method

Complex 3				
$E_{\text{excitation}}$ (eV)	$\lambda_{\text{excitation}}$ (nm)	Osc. strength (f)	Key excitations	Character
2.6649	465.2	0.0002	(98%)HOMO→LUMO	L ¹ (π)/Ru($d\pi$)→L ¹ (π^*)
3.1177	397.7	0.1668	(41%)HOMO-2→LUMO+1 (40%)HOMO-1→LUMO	L ¹ (π)/Ru($d\pi$)→L ¹ (π^*)
3.4880	352.4	0.3460	(82%)HOMO→LUMO+2	L ¹ (π)/Ru($d\pi$)→L ¹ (π^*)
4.1046	302.1	0.0787	(96%)HOMO-3→LUMO	L ¹ (π)→L ¹ (π^*)
4.5804	270.7	0.0544	(59%)HOMO-6→LUMO	L ¹ (π)→L ¹ (π^*)
4.7885	258.9	0.1361	(60%)HOMO-7→LUMO	L ¹ (π)→L ¹ (π^*)
4.7905	258.8	0.1345	(59%)HOMO-7→LUMO+1	L ¹ (π)→L ¹ (π^*)
4.8136	257.6	0.1433	(85%)HOMO-3→LUMO+3	L ¹ (π)→L ¹ (π^*)
Complex 4				
2.8900	429.0	0.0009	(96%)HOMO→LUMO	L ² (π)/Ru($d\pi$)→L ² (π^*)
3.1555	392.9	0.2413	(47%)HOMO-2→LUMO+1 (47%)HOMO-1→LUMO	L ² (π)/Ru($d\pi$)→L ² (π^*)
3.7288	342.5	0.2055	(94%)HOMO→LUMO+2	L ² (π)/Ru($d\pi$)→L ² (π^*)
3.9063	317.4	0.2181	(69%)HOMO-3→LUMO	L ² (π)→L ² (π^*)
4.2440	292.1	0.4765	(88%)HOMO-4→LUMO+1	L ² (π)→L ² (π^*)
4.5810	270.7	0.1408	(69%)HOMO-7→LUMO	L ² (π)→L ² (π^*)

$d\pi(\text{Ru}) \rightarrow \pi^*(\text{L})$ (MLCT) and $\pi(\text{L}) \rightarrow \pi^*(\text{L})$ (ILCT) transitions. Again, the peak at ~ 340 nm has ILCT character

along with large contribution of MLCT transition. The close by peaks at ~ 290 and ~ 260 nm have ILCT character.

Conclusion

In summary, we designed and synthesized two pyrazine functionalized Ru^{II}-NHC complexes of *N*-methylimidazolylidene (**3**) and *N*-methylbenzimidazolylidene (**4**). Geometry of both the complexes are optimized to their ground state energy minima, bond parameters are found consistence with the reported data. Absorption and emission spectra of both complexes were studied. The peaks are due to ILCT character along with large contribution of MLCT transition in complexes. Electrochemistry, emission spectra of the compounds has been studied. The voltammetry feature of complexes **3** and **4** are quasireversible to irreversible. Both complexes are fluorescence active in nature.

Experimental

Reagents, chemicals and instrumental :

All the reactions were carried out under nitrogen using standard Schlenk-type flask. Workup procedures were done in air. All the solvents and chemicals were purchased and used without further purification. The chemicals were purchased from Sigma Aldrich, Lancaster, UK and Aurora Metthy, Kolkata. ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker 400 spectrometer. Chemical shifts, δ in ppm are reported to the internal standard TMS for ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR. Microanalyses were performed on a Perkin-Elmer model 2400 instrument, electronic absorption measurements were done with Varian Cary 1 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. To obtain MALDI mass spectra, a Voyager time-of-flight mass spectrometer (Applied Biosystem, USA), equipped with 337 nm N₂ laser was used and operated in accelerating voltage 20 kV. The spectra were recorded in the positive ion linear mode. Reproducibility of the spectrum was checked 5 times from separately spotted samples.

General synthesis :

*Synthesis of ligand [2,6-bis-(*N*-methylimidazolium)-pyrazine]dichloride, **1** :*

The ligand [2,6-bis-(1-methylimidazolium)pyrazine]dichloride, **1**, was synthesized by the reported procedure^{6,36}. 2,6-Dichloropyrazine (2.00 g, 13.42 mmol) was added to 1-methylimidazole (2.20 g, 26.83 mmol) under neat leads to chloride salt, fume was observed and the mixture became hot. The wet solid were heated neat at

75 °C with stirring for 1.5 h. The crude yellowish solid product was triturated in THF and washed with diethylether to get the pure white mass of ligand **1**. Yield; 3.61 g (11.54 mmol, 86%). ¹H NMR (CD₃CN, 25 °C, 400 Mz) : δ 9.47 (2H, s, H^{a1}), 9.24 (2H, s, H^{b1}), 8.27 (2H, d, *J* 3.2 Hz, H^{c1}), 7.67 (2H, d, *J* 2.0 Hz, H^{d1}), 4.02 (6H, s, N-CH₃); ¹³C NMR (CD₃CN, 400 MHz) : 140.7 (C2-Pz), 136.3 (C3-Pz), 135.4 (NCN), 125.34 (C4-imi), 119.3 (C5-imi), 36.7 (N-CH₃). Mass *m/z*⁺ = 313.2 [L], 241.8 [L]²⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₄N₆Cl₂ : C, 46.02; H, 4.50; N, 26.83. Found : C, 45.98; H, 4.48; N, 26.79%.

*Synthesis of ligand [2,6-bis-(*N*-methylbenzimidazolium)-pyrazine]dichloride, **2** :*

Ligand **2** was synthesized by the reported procedure⁶ when 2,6-dichloropyrazine (2.00 g, 13.42 mmol) was added to 1-methylbenzimidazole (3.55 g, 26.84 mmol) and the mixture is heated neat at 125 °C with stirring for 4 h and the mixture became solid. The crude yellowish solid product was triturated in THF and washed with diethylether to get the pure white mass of [2,6-bis-(*N*-methylbenzimidazolium)pyrazine]dichloride. Yield; 4.44 g (11.72 mmol, 80%). ¹H NMR (CD₃CN, 25 °C, 400 Mz) : δ 9.97 (2H, s, H^a), 9.59 (2H, s, H^b), 8.61 (2H, d, ²*J* 7.9 Hz, H^c), 8.26 (2H, d, ²*J* 7.5 Hz, H^f), 8.02 (4H, m, ²*J* 42.76 Hz, H^{d,e}), 4.27 (6H, s, N-CH₃); ¹³C NMR (CD₃CN, 400 MHz) : 144.3 (2Pz), 144.0 (3Pz), 139.9 (NCN), 130.0, 129.4, 118.5, 116.7, 115.9, 115.2 (Ar-C), 34.8 (N-CH₃). Mass *m/z*⁺ = 413.3 [L], 341.6 [L]²⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₈N₆Cl₂ : C, 58.12; H, 4.39; N, 20.33. Found : C, 58.09; H, 4.36; N, 20.29%.

*Synthesis of complex bis-[2,6-di-(*N*-methylimidazo-2-ylidene)pyrazine]ruthenium(II) hexafluorophosphate, **3** :*

A mixture of RuCl₃·3H₂O (0.3 g, 1.15 mmol) and the proligand **1** (1.22 g, 2.29 mmol) in 5 ml ethylene glycol was refluxed at 180 °C for 6 h. The resulting solution becomes brown red to dark, the solution left to cool for 1 h and transfer to a 100 ml beaker. To this solution a saturated aqueous solution of KPF₆ was added and immediate a brown red ppt. was observed of complex **3**. The ppt. was filtered, dried and subjected to column chromatography. The orange red mass was eluted in CH₃CN : CHCl₃ (2 : 1). The product was re-crystallized from acetonitrile and diethyl ether. Yield; 0.506 g (0.58 mmol, 58%). ¹H NMR (CD₃CN, 25 °C, 400 Mz) : δ 9.13 (2H,

s, H^{b1}), 8.17 (1H, d, ²J 4.4 Hz, H^{c1}), 7.07 (1H, d, J 4.8 Hz, H^{d1}), 3.13 (1H, s, N-CH₃); ¹³C NMR (CD₃CN, 400 MHz) : 142.88 (C2Pz), 138.46 (C3Pz), 136.54 (NCN), 126.63 (C4-imi), 121.22 (C5-imi), 37.62 (N-CH₃). Mass m/z^+ = 582.2 [Ru(L)₂]⁺², 242.2 [L]²⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₄H₂₄N₁₂RuP₂F₁₂ : C, 33.03; H, 2.75; N, 19.27. Found : C, 32.99; H, 2.74; N, 19.25%.

Synthesis complex bis-[2,6-di-(N-methylbenzimidazo-2-ylidene)pyrazine]ruthenium(II) hexafluorophosphate, 4 :

Synthesis of complex **4** is similar to **3**. A mixture RuCl₃·3H₂O (0.3 g, 1.15 mmol) and the proligand, **2** (1.49 g, 2.3 mmol) in 5 ml ethylene glycol was refluxed at 180 °C for 6 h. The resulting solution becomes brown red to dark, the solution left to cool for one hour, and transfer to a 100 ml beaker and rest of the procedure similar to **3**. The orange red mass was eluted in CH₃CN : CHCl₃ (3 : 1). The product was re-crystallized from acetonitrile and diethyl ether. Yield; 0.546 g (0.51 mmol, 51%). ¹H NMR (CD₃CN, 25 °C, 400 Mz) : δ 9.33 (2H, s, H^b), 8.32 (2H, d, ²J 5.72 Hz, H^c), 7.46 (2H, d, ²J 5.28 Hz, H^f), 7.35 (4H, m, ²J 12.2 Hz, H^{d,e}), 4.92 (6H, s, N-CH₃); ¹³C NMR (CD₃CN, 400 MHz) : 148.94 (2Pz), 146.62 (3Pz), 142.36 (NCN), 131.59, 130.21, 120.21, 118.11, 117.21, 116.49 (Ar-C), 36.93 (N-CH₃) [Fig. 4b]. Mass m/z^+ = 781.7 [Ru(L)₂]⁺², 341.2 [L]²⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₄₀H₃₂N₁₂RuP₂F₁₂ : C, 44.78; H, 2.99; N, 15.67. Found : C, 44.76; H, 2.97; N, 15.66%.

Structure determination :

X-Ray data of complex **3** was collected on a CCD diffractometer (graphite monochromated Mo K α radiation, $k = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) by use of ω scans. The structures were solved by direct methods and refined on F2 using all reflections with SHELX-97. The nonhydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. Hydrogen atoms which were not bound to imidazolium-C2 atoms were placed in calculated positions and assigned to an isotropic displacement parameter of 0.08 Å. To compare the bond parameters, geometry of complex **3** also optimized in DFT technic using Gaussian03-E01⁴⁴ software. In order to understand the structure of synthesized complex **4**, the structure was drawn according to the NMR and Mass data found, and also further generated the optimized structure of complexes **4** (correlating with the structure of complex **3**) with DFT technic.

Electrochemistry and spectral study :

The electrochemical properties of the complexes are investigated by cyclic voltammetry in acetonitrile solution at scan rate 50 mV s⁻¹ using 0.1 M [*n*-Bu₄N][ClO₄] as supporting electrolyte. Data were collected under nitrogen environment. The potentials are expressed with reference to Ag/AgCl. The voltammograms of **3** and **4** are shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Cyclovoltammogram of 1 mM complex **3** and 1 mM **4** in CH₃CN solution containing 0.1 M [*n*-Bu₄N][ClO₄] at scan rate 50 mV s⁻¹, temp. 25°, electrode potential in mV vs saturated Ag/AgCl electrode.

Fig. 6. Absorption and emission spectra of **3** (—) and **4** (.....) in acetonitrile solvent.

Table 6. Spectral data of complexes **3** and **4**

Complex	λ_{max} (nm) (ϵ , $\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	$\lambda_{\text{emission}}$ (nm)
3	409 (13345), 342 (11497), 297 (16369), 364 (19272)	564
4	400 (11364), 340 (9098), 288 (15496), 261 (20144)	556

The nature of voltammogram does not change with scan rate (50–200 mV s^{-1}). Electronic absorption measurements were done using acetonitrile as solvent with Varian Cary 1 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Emission spectra were recorded using same solvent with Perkin-Elmer LS-45 Fluorescence Spectrometer.

DFT analysis :

All computations were performed using the Gaussian03-E01⁴⁴ software package. Full geometry optimizations were carried out using the density functional theory method at the B3LYP level^{45,46} for complexes **3** and **4**. The calculations were performed by using the LANL2DZ effective potential (ECP) set of Hay and Wadt⁴⁷ for ruthenium atom and the standard 6-31+G(d) basis for C, H and N atoms. The vibrational frequency calculations were performed to ensure that the optimized geometries represent the local minima and there are only positive eigen values. Vertical electronic excitations based on B3LYP optimized geometries were computed using the time-dependent density functional theory (TDDFT) formalism⁴⁸⁻⁵¹ in acetonitrile using conductor-like polarizable continuum model (CPCM)^{52,53} using the same B3LYP level and basis sets. GaussSum54 was used to calculate

the fractional contributions of various groups to each molecular orbital.

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